

Determination of Lercanidipine hydrochloride, an antihypertensive agent via coordination complexation using cobalt thiocyanate

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Abstract : A simple and sensitive extractive spectrophotometric method has been developed for the assay of Lercanidipine hydrochloride, an antihypertensive agent in bulk and formulations. The method is based on the formation of colored species between the drug and cobalt thiocyanate (CTC) by formation of coordination complex which can be extractable in nitrobenzene. The absorbance was measured at 620 nm and the method has been analyzed statistically. The system obeyed the Beer's law in the range 5–25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Molar absorptivity values were found to be $1.367 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The limit of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were found to be $10.3 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and $31.3 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ respectively. Precision (% RSD) and accuracy (recoveries range from $98.6 \pm 1.3 - 100.8 \pm 1.0\%$) of the developed method was evaluated.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, Lercanidipine hydrochloride (LER), Lerez, Lerka, nitrobenzene, cobalt thiocyanate.

Introduction

Lercanidipine hydrochloride (LER) is chemically 2-[(3,3-diphenylpropyl)(methyl)amino]-1,1-dimethylethyl methyl-2,6-dimethyl-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (Fig. 1). This drug is used as a calcium channel blocker in the treatment of hypertension¹. Number of analytical methods have been reported

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of Lercanidipine hydrochloride.

in literature for the estimation of LER. These methods include HPLC²⁻⁷, TLC⁸, voltammetry^{9,10} and few spectrophotometric methods¹¹⁻²⁴. The authors have developed simple and sensitive visible extraction-spectrophotometric method for quantitative determination of LER in bulk drug and formulations.

Experimental

Apparatus :

All spectral and absorbance measurements were made on a Elico SL-177 model visible spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched glass cells and on UNICAM UV 500 spectrophotometer made by Thermo Electron Corporation. All pH measurements were made on an Elico LI 120 digital pH meter.

Reagents and materials :

All the reagents were of analytical grade and all solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Aqueous solutions of cobalt thiocyanate (BDH; $2.5 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$), buffer solution (pH 2.0) and nitrobenzene (Qualigens) solvent are used. The bulk drug Lercanidipine hydrochloride (Sun Pharmaceutical Ind. Ltd., India) was selected for the study. Two formulations, Lerka (Sun Pharmaceutical Ind. Ltd., India) and Lerez (Glenmark, India) containing Lercanidipine hydrochloride were purchased from local commercial sources. Tablets equivalent to 10 mg of different batches of two formulations were selected for this study.

Reduction of Lercanidipine hydrochloride (bulk sample) :

About 100 mg of bulk drug was dissolved in 10.0 mL methanol and reduced using standard literature method²⁵.

Standard drug solution (bulk sample) :

The reduced drug solution in methanol was evaporated to dryness. The free base stock solution (mg/ml) was prepared by mixing 100 mg of the reduced bulk drug with 10.0 ml of 10% Na₂CO₃ solution. The resulting solution was transferred into 150 ml separating funnel and extracted with 3 × 25 ml portions of chloroform and combined chloroform layer was brought up to 100 ml with chloroform. This free base stock solution was further diluted step wise with chloroform to obtain working standard solution of 100 mg/ml.

Formulations (Lerka and Lerez) :

Since only two formulations Lerka 10 mg (Sun Pharmaceutical Ind. Ltd., India) and Lerez 10 mg (Glenmark, India) are available for LER (tablets), these formulations of different batches were collected and analyzed as 4 sets to verify the validity of proposed method. Accurately weighed quantity of tablet powder equivalent to 100 mg of LER was extracted with warm chloroform (3 × 25.0 mL) and filtered. The combined extract was evaporated and reduced using standard literature method¹³. The reduced drug solution in methanol was evaporated to dryness. The free base stock solution (mg/ml) was prepared as described in the case of bulk drug and further diluted step wise with the same solvent to obtain working standard solution of 100 µg/ml. An appropriate aliquots of the solution was treated as mentioned in the general procedure to test the validity of method developed. The UV spectrophotometric method has been chosen as the reference method for ascertaining the accuracy of the proposed methods.

Analytical procedure :

Aliquots of standard drug (free base form) solution (0.5–2.5 ml, 100 µg ml⁻¹), were delivered into series of calibrated tubes and solvent was completely removed by gentle heating on a boiling water bath. To the residue in each tube, 2.0 ml of buffer (pH 2.0) and 5.0 ml of 2.5 × 10⁻¹ M CTC solutions were added. The total volume of aqueous phase in each separating funnel was adjusted to 15.0 ml with distilled water. These solutions in the test tubes were transferred to 125 ml separating funnels. To

each separating funnel 10.0 ml of nitrobenzene was added and the contents were shaken for 2 min. The two phases were allowed to separate and the absorbances of the separated nitrobenzene layer were measured at 620 nm against a similar reagent blank after 10 min. The amount of drug was deduced from its calibration curve (Fig. 3).

Results and discussion

Optimization studies :

The optimum conditions for each method were established by varying one parameter at a time and keeping the others fixed and observing the effect produced on the absorbance of the coloured species. The effects of various parameters such as buffer solution, concentration of the CTC, organic solvent used for extraction, ratio of organic to aqueous phase during extraction, stability period and intensity of colored species were studied. The optimum conditions were as follows : 4.5–6.5 mL (1.1–1.6 × 10⁻¹ mol L⁻¹) of CTC solution, 1.5–2.5 mL (1.5–2.5 × 10⁻² mol L⁻¹) of buffer solution (pH 2.0), 1–4 min of shaking time, the ratio of aqueous to organic phase on extraction is 3 : 2 were found to be optimal. In the procedure, 5.0 mL of (1.3 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹) CTC, 2.0 mL (2.0 × 10⁻² mol L⁻¹) buffer solution and 2 min shaking period required for maximum color development were found to be optimum conditions. The other water immiscible solvents tested for the extraction of the coloured complex into organic phase include chlorobenzene, dichloromethane, dichlorobenzene and nitrobenzene. Nitrobenzene was preferred for its selective extraction of the complex from the aqueous phase due to its higher sensitivity. The ratio of aqueous to organic phase on extraction was taken as 3 : 2. The colored species were stable for 40 min. The λ_{max} (nm) and ε_{max} (L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) values were found to be 620 and 1.36 × 10⁴ respectively.

Selection of analytical wavelength :

For the selection of analytical wavelength, 100 µg ml⁻¹ solution of Lercanidipine hydrochloride was prepared by appropriate dilution of standard stock solution and scanned in the spectrum mode from 800–400 nm. The spectrum of the colored species produced by the suggested procedure is shown to possess maximum absorbance at 620 nm which was selected for the analysis

(Fig. 2). The calibration curve was prepared in the concentration range of 5–25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ at 620 nm. By using the calibration curve (Fig. 3), the concentration of the sample solution can be determined. The linearity was found in the concentration range of 5–25 mg ml^{-1} as shown in the Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectrum of LER-CTC method.

Fig. 3. Beer's law plot of LER-CTC method.

Mechanism of reaction :

The colored species formed can be regarded as a coordinate complex of the drug (Lewis base) and the central metal atom of cobalt thiocyanate (Lewis acid) which is extractable into nitrobenzene from aqueous solution. Formation of the blue coloured complexes when LER is treated with CTC due to the presence of aliphatic tertiary amino group is the basis in the present investigation. It was observed that the drug (LER), cobalt and thiocyanate were in the ratio of 2 : 1 : 4 in the complex. The probable sequence of reactions based on analogy in previous work is presented in Scheme^{26, 27}.

Validation studies :

The developed method was validated as per ICH guidelines²⁸ for its linearity, precision, accuracy, limit of detection and limit of quantification. Regression analysis using the method of least square was made to evaluate the slope (b), intercept (a), and correlation coefficient (R) obtained from different concentrations of drug. The result of slope (2.12×10^{-2}) and intercept (-6.0×10^{-4}) of drug by the proposed method was given in Table 1. Linearity was found in the concentration range 5–25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Beer's law plots ($n = 6$) were linear with a correlation coefficient of 0.9999 (Table 1). Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were established according to ICH guidelines²⁸ and determined by using the formula $\text{LOD} = K.SDa/b$ where $K = 3.3$ for LOD and 10 for LOQ. SDa is the standard deviation of the intercept and b is the slope of the calibration line. LOD

Scheme. Formation of coordination complex between LER and CTC.

Table 1. Analytical and validation parameters for LER with CTC method

Name of the parameter	Lercandipine
λ_{\max} (nm)	620
Beer's Law limits ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	5–25
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	1.36×10^4
Limit of detection ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	10.3×10^{-2}
Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	31.3×10^{-2}
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g/cm}^2/$ 0.001 Absorbance unit)	4.74×10^{-2}
Regression equation ($Y = a + bC$) ^a	
Slope (b)	2.12×10^{-2}
Standard deviation on slope (S_b)	4.0×10^{-5}
Intercept (a)	-6.0×10^{-4}
Standard deviation on intercept (S_a)	6.63×10^{-4}
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9999

^a $Y = a + bC$, where C is the concentration of analyte in $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and Y is the absorbance unit.

Table 2. Evaluation of precision and accuracy of proposed method

Name of the parameter	Lercandipine
Precision (RSD, %) ^a	
Intra-day reproducibility (RSD, %)	0.98
Inter-day reproducibility (RSD, %)	0.95
% Range of error ^b	
Confidence limit at 0.05 level (95%)	± 1.02
Confidence limit at 0.01 level (99%)	± 1.60

^aAverage of six determinations ($n = 6$); ^bLER concentration : 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

and LOQ were found to be as low as 10.3×10^{-2} and $31.3 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ respectively (Table 1). The precision of the proposed method was studied by repeating the method six times ($n = 6$). To study intra-day precision, the method was repeated six times a day. Similarly, the method was repeated on six consecutive days to determine inter-day precision (Table 2). The accuracy of the method was determined in terms of % recovery of LER standard. Recovery studies were carried out by addition of standard drug solution at three different levels (8, 10, 12 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) to previously analyzed sample (tablet) solution. Values of recovery \pm SD were found to be in the range of 99.7 ± 0.4 – 100.4 ± 0.4 for Lerez and Lerka tablets ($n = 3$). The extents of interference by various excipients that often accompany pharmaceutical formulations are analyzed. The high percentage of recovery showed that excipients did not interfere with the proposed method.

Application of the proposed method :

The application of the proposed method for the assay of pharmaceutical formulations was examined for tablets and the results were statistically compared with those obtained by UV reference method. The results obtained by the proposed and UV reference method for the formulations were compared by means of Student's t -test and F -test and was found that the proposed method do not differ significantly in precision and accuracy. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Assay of Lercandipine in pharmaceutical formulations

Formulations	Labelled amount (mg)	Amount found by proposed method (mg) ^{a,b} (CTC)	F -test value	t -test value	Reference method ^c	% Recovery by proposed method ^d (CTC)
Lerka (Batch-I)	10	9.87 ± 0.13	1.68	1.89	9.96 ± 0.10	98.66 ± 1.3
Lerka (Batch-II)	10	10.08 ± 0.09	1.59	0.24	10.07 ± 0.12	100.8 ± 1.0
Lerez (Batch-III)	10	10.14 ± 0.12	1.06	1.69	9.92 ± 0.12	99.66 ± 1.2
Lerez (Batch-IV)	10	9.88 ± 0.08	2.27	0.71	9.92 ± 0.12	98.82 ± 0.76

^aMean \pm SD ($n = 6$). ^bTheoretical values of 95% confidence limit, $F = 5.05$, $t = 2.57$. ^cMean \pm SD ($n = 3$). ^dAverage of three determinations ($n = 3$).

Table 4. Comparison of proposed method with reported methods for Lercanidipine

Reagents used	λ_{\max} (nm)	Beer's law limits (mg ml ⁻¹)	Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>)	Molar absorptivity (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	LOD (µg mL ⁻¹)	LOQ (µg mL ⁻¹)	Reference
HNO ₂ /1-NPA	530	5–25	0.9989	0.463×10^4	NA	NA	15
Fe(NO ₃) ₃	390	5–25	0.9978	1.468×10^4	NA	NA	15
M.O	425	5–25	0.9978	1.84×10^4	NA	NA	16
CTC	620	5–25	0.9999	1.36×10^4	10.3×10^{-2}	31.3×10^{-2}	Present paper

1-NPA : 1-Naphthylamine, M.O : Methyl Orange, CTC : Cobalt thiocyanate, NED : N-(1-naphthyl)ethylene diamine dihydrochloride.

The results obtained by the proposed method are compared with reported methods^{15,16} and found to be more sensitive in the range of 5–25 µg ml⁻¹ with ϵ_{\max} value 1.36×10^4 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Other analytical parameters like limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were also evaluated for proposed method and compared with reported methods (Table 4). The proposed method requires less expensive equipment, low cost reagents and also free from stringent conditional procedures.

Conclusions

The importance lies in the chemical reactions upon which the procedures are based rather than upon the sophistication of the instrument. The proposed method is simple, sensitive, accurate with a correlation coefficient value 0.9999 and precise enough to be successfully adopted as an alternative method of GLC or HPLC technique and as well as the existing spectrophotometric methods for routine analysis and in formulations.

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